

EXPORTABLE INDIAN COMMODITIES IN THE ACCOUNTS OF EARLY ARAB WRITERS

Zubair Mohammad Ehsanul Hoque*

Abstract

Trade relations between India and Arabia were extensive in the period before the advent of Islam. These commercial relations increased after the rise of Islam. With the spread of writing tradition among the Arabs some voyagers started to preserve their experiences in the form of books. These books contain description of trade routes, sea-ports and commercial commodities. In this paper an attempt has been taken to present a brief account on Indian (including Bengal) commodities according to the description of early Arab geographers and travellers. The paper will explore the position of India and Bengal in international trade in those early days.

Introduction

This is well-known that commerce of Arabia with India and Bengal is time-worn. Commercial ships had been frequenting between Arabian ports and southern coast of India. With the advent of Islam Arabs' seafaring got a new dimension, as a new purpose was added in seafaring that was preaching of Islam. Gradually the Arabs took the control of sea trade of Indian Ocean in their grip. Their sway continued until the arrival of the Europeans in the early 15th century. With the emergence of the Portuguese ships in the 15th century the dominance of the Arabs over Indian Ocean started to decline.

During the period of their dominance some Arab writers registered experiences of their voyages in their books. The first of its kind was written in the middle of the 9th century by a famous traveller, named Sulaiman the Merchant (851), who made a two-way sea journey from Arabia to China touching the Indian coast. In later periods more accounts of voyages appeared regularly. Those writings were not merely travel-literature. The writers intended to make their books guides for traders; so,

* Associate Professor, Department of Arabic, University of Dhaka

they furnished them with the information of ports, trade-centres and commodities found there. Obviously, the description of Indian (also Bengal) ports and their commodities found place there.

This paper offers a list of goods and commodities traded by India and Bengal. The writers on which we depend are of three categories: a) travellers such as Sulaiman, whose accounts were sheer descriptions of his navigational experiences; b) geographers such as al-Mas'udi (896-956), who was also famous as a traveller, and a historian; and c) geographers such as Ibn Khurdzbeh (820-912). The paper will reveal contribution of India and Bengal to international trade in those early days. I have gathered scattered information of Arab writers and presented it in a combined fashion. The items of products will be presented in alphabetical order.

1. Aloe (العود): Aloe was the most attractive Indian product which drew the interest of Arab geographers and travellers. They described it elaborately including its types and qualities. It came from post-equator islands; however its tree, leaves or plantation system were not known to the Arabs. The water brings aloes in the direction of the north.¹ There are several types of aloes, among them seven types are mentionable:

1.1. Hindi Aloe (العود الهندي) dried in the sea and was thrown ashore in a withered condition. It was strong and thick. To put it to test, it was filled and tossed upon water; if it did not submerge in water, it was not of ideal quality. If it submerged in water, it was of immaculate quality and there was nothing superior to that.² Hindi aloe was found in Rahma³ and Tayuma.⁴

1.2. Mandali Aloe (العود المنديلي): This is only Qazwini (1203-1283) who mentions a type of aloe named *Mandali aloe* which was obtained in Mandal,⁵ however it did not grow there and its origin was not known to anyone. Yet, people related it to islands beyond the equator. It came to

1 H. M. Elliot & John Dowson, *The History of India as told by its own Historians*, (London: Trubner & Co. 1867) p. 96; S Muhammad Hussayn Nainar, *Arab Geographers' Knowledge of Southern India*, (Madras: The University of Madras, 1942), p. 184.

2 Nainar, *Op. cit.*, p. 185.

3 This is the unanimous *Opinion* of the historians that Rahma or Ruhmi (رهمي) should be identified with Bengal. (Elliot & Dowson, *Op. cit.*, p. 361.

4 Ibn Khurdzbeh (ed. M. J. De. Goeje), *Kitab al-Masalikwa al-Mumalik* (Leiden: E. J. Brill, 1967), pp. 67-68.

5 Location of this place has not been identified in modern map.

the north by sea-stream. It was heavy and hard after becoming dry. People tested it by throwing it in water, if the aloe submerged in water that was of the best quality and nothing was superior to it.⁶

1.3. Qāmaruni Aloe (العود القامروني): Qāmarun⁷ was a neighboring kingdom of Ruhmi (Bengal).⁸ Its hilly areas produced aloes of superior quality and of pleasant fragrance.⁹ *Qāmaruni aloe* was imported to Samandar¹⁰ from a distance of fifteen to twenty days' journey through a river of which the waters were sweet.¹¹ This species drew the attention of traders from all over India and outsides. Some pilgrims conveyed *Qāmaruni aloe* as an offering to the idol of Multan and donated it to the clerics for the purpose of incensing the idol. From the priests, generally, the merchants purchased this quality of aloe which costs about two hundred *dinars* per *mann*. It often received the imprint of seal like wax to preserve its quality.¹²

1.4. Qumari Aloe (العود القماري): *Qumari aloe*, which was full grown and well-soaked in plentiful water, was produced in and exported from a place named *Qumar*.¹³ This quality was dried in its growing place and was torn in the sea. The Kingdom of Multan earned huge amount of revenue from *Qumari aloe* although it did not produce this plant. Al-

6. فإن رسب في الماء فهو غاية جدا ليس فوقه خير منه Qazwini (ed. Ferdinand Wüstenfeld), *'Ajaib al-Makhlūqat wa Garaib al-Mawjudat* (Göttingen: Druck und Verlag der Dieterichschen Buchhandlung, 1848). 2:71

7. There is no doubt that Qāmarun is a corruption of Kamarupa, the mediaeval term for Assam.

8. Ibn Khurdzbeh, *Op. cit.*, p. 67.

9. وهناك منابت عود جيد في بخوره ويجلب هناك من جبال قامرون Al-Idrisi, *Nujhah al-Mushtaq fi Ikhtiraq al-Afaq* (Cairo: Maktaba al-Thaqafa al-Diniyyah, 2002) p.192-93.

10. Karim claims firmly that Samandar should be identified with Chittagong and the sweet water, referred by Al-Idrisi and Ibn Khurdzbeh, is nothing but the river Brahmaputra. Abdul Karim, *Social History of the Muslims in Bengal (Down to A.D. 1538)* (Chittagong: BSIRC 1985), p. 31

11. يحمل إليها العود من مسيرة خمسة عشر يوما وعشرين يوما في ماء عذب من كامرون . Ibn Khurdzbeh, *Op.cit.*, pp. 63-64.

12. يحمل الرّجل منهم العود الهندي القامروني، حتى يأتي به إلى هذا الصّتم فيدفعه إلى السدنة منه مائتي دينار، فالتجار يبتاعونه من هؤلاء لبخور الصنم، ومن هذا العود ما قيمة المنا السدنة Al-Sirafi, *Rihla al-Sirafi*, (Abu Dhabi: Al-Mujamma' al-Thaqafi 1999). p. 85

13. القمار وهي الأرض التي يجلب Ibn Khurdzbeh, *Op. cit.*, p. 68; وبقمار العود القماري منها العود القماري Abu Zayd, *Op. cit.*, p. 68. The identification of Qumar is not certain; however, Nainar thinks that the term may be associated either with Khumayr (Cambodia) or Cape Comorin. Nainar, *Op. cit.*, 187.

Mas'udi says: 'the greatest part of the revenue of the king of Multan is derived from the rich present brought to the idol of the pure aloe-wood of Kumar, which is of the finest quality, and one *mann* of which is worth 200 dinars, for it is so genuine that it receives the impression of seal like wax.'¹⁴ According to Mas'udi and Qazwini *Qumari aloe* is the best variety.

1.5. Qaquilli Aloe (العود القافلي): The reference to this genus of Indian aloes appears only in Ya'qubi's (897) *Fragmenta*, but he provides nothing other than the name.¹⁵

1.6. Şanfı Aloe (العود الصنفي): Şanfı aloe was obtained in Şanf, a land towards the direction of China.¹⁶ There are two contrasting views on Şanfı aloe. Ya'qubi refers to few traders who hold that '*Şanfı aloe* is better than *Qaquilli aloe*, and it has more delicious fragrance, clinging and safe from attracting others by its odor.'¹⁷ There are also some who rank it above *Qumari aloe* for it sinks in water because it is good and heavy.¹⁸

By contrast, Qazwini regards Şanfı aloe as the most ordinary quality. According to him there is very little difference between it and normal wood.¹⁹

1.7. Saymuri Aloe (العود الصيموري): Yaqut (1179-1229) and Qazwini mention a species of aloe which is obtained in Saymur²⁰ and they do not provide any details.

We want to make one thing clear that the aloe mentioned by the Arab writers is not aloe vera (*NZKḡwix*); rather this is agarwood, which is also known as oud, oodh, aloeswood and agar (*ʔwMIMVQ*). The resin of this tree had been used to produce perfume and aromatic smoke in ancient and

وأكثر أموال صاحب الملتان مما يحمل إلى هذا الصنم من العود القماري الخالص الذي يبلغ ثمن الأوقية 14 منه مائة دينار وإذا ختم بالخاتم أثر فيه كما يؤثر في الشمع. Al-Mas'udi, *Muruj al-Dhahab*, (Beirut: Al-Maktabah al- 'Asriyyah, 2005), v. 1, p. 130.

15 Nainar, *Op. cit.*, p. 183.

16 Şanf is identified with Champa.

17 Nainar, *Op. cit.*, p. 183.

18 وبها العود الصنفي وهو أفضل من القماري لأنه يغرق في الماء لجودته وثقله. Ibn Khurdzbeh, *Op. cit.*, p. 68.

19 Al-Qazwini, *Op. cit.*, 2: 64.

20 Qazwini, *Op. cit.*, 2:64. Saymur may be identified with Shirur, a municipal council in the Pune district of the Indian state of Maharashtra, which is located on the banks of the River Ghod.

medieval ages (also in modern age). The account of Arab travellers indicates that aloe wood is produced in many Indian kingdoms. This product occupies a prominent place in international trade and acts as an important source of revenue for kings as has already been mentioned by the authority of al-Mas'udi. This fact is endorsed by Yaqut who tells that the kings alongside the seashore take a tenth of the amount of aloes from the individuals who gather them on the shorelines.²¹

2. Ambergris(عنبر): Arab writers mention detailed information on ambergris including its growing place, types and processes of its collection.

Ambergris or '*anbar*' is a substance, which grows in mountains in the bottoms of the sea. It is as big as the size of a camel or of a big rock.²² '*Anbars*' are of different colours such as white, black and dark bay colour. They are uprooted by the wind and violence of the waves during the winter season and thrown on the shore. They will be boiling ferociously and none could approach them because of the severity of heat and boiling. After a break of time wind beats on them and they become solidified. Then the people in the adjacent littoral land collect them.

Anber is of different types²³ depending on its resin. One of them is *anbar-hindi*, which is also branded as Karbalus, associated with the community known as Karbalus. The collectors carry it to some place near Oman where the captains buy it from them. This is also exported to Basra, Siraf and other places.²⁴

3. Bamboo (خيزران):²⁵ Arab writers merely mention that bamboo grows in abundance in some Indian lands such as Kulam²⁶ and Sandan.²⁷

21 Nainar, *Op. cit.*, p. 185.

22 This is told by Ya'qubi; according to Abu Zaydits size is like a house.

ويقع في هذه الجزائر عنبر عظيم القدر، فتقع القطعة مثل البيت ونحوه، وهذا العنبر ينبت في قعر البحر نباتا، فإذا اشتد هيجان البحر قذفه من قعره مثل الفطر والكمأة
Abu Zayd, *Op. cit.*, p. 17.

23 Other types include a) '*Anbar Shuhri*' (the best quality) produced on the coast of Shuhr; b) '*Anbar samaki*' – obtained through a fish; c) '*Anbar manakiri*' – obtained through khattaf a kind of sparrow; d) '*Anbar-zanji*' – that which comes from the Zanj to Aden; e) '*Anbar-Shalahit*' and f) '*Anbar-ququlli*'. See Nainar, *Op. cit.*, p. 188.

24 Al-Mas'udi, *Op. cit.*, pp. 117-18.

25 Al-Idrisi, *Op. cit.*, p. 182.

26 There is no doubt that Kulam is associated with Kollam, an old seaport and city on the Laccavide sea coast in Indian state of Kerala.

4. **Banana (موز)**: Bananas are produced in many kingdoms and islands of India namely in Bullin,²⁸ Sandan and Saymur.²⁹

5. **Brazil Wood (بغم)**: see logwood.

6. **Canna Indica (قنا)**: Canna Indica, a native plant of India, is grown all over this country especially in hilly areas of Utkin,³⁰ Sindan, Mulai, Barus, Tana and Kuli.³¹

7. **Camphor (كافور)**: Camphor is obtained on the incline of a mountain between Kulam (Kollam) and Mandurqin (Madura). However, the best quality is obtained in and exported from Faysur.

Camphor is the kernel of the tree. The tree is cleft and camphor is taken from inside. Sometimes it is soft, sometimes hard, for it is the resin in the heart of the tree. If the rind is injured the camphor will flow from inside; if it is split, great pieces may be obtained from the interior, but it forces the tree to dwindle and to die.³²

As indicated by Qazwini, the camphor acquired in Faysur is the best quality. It is said that camphor is found in substantial amounts in the years when there is much thunder, lighting and tremor. In less stormy years the camphor is found in less amounts.³³

8. **Chalk (طباشير)**: *Tabashir* (chalk) is not a plant; rather it is a product extracted from cannas and bamboos. The extraction procedure of *tabashir* is as follows:

The real article of *tabashir* is extracted from the roots of Indian canna. In the forest when cannas and bamboos become dried up, and the wind

27 Sandan is identified with Sindhudurg, an administrative district in the state of Maharashtra in India. Nainar, *Op. cit.*, p. 68

28 Professor Minorsky suggests on the authority of Dr Barnett that Bullin is Baliapatam in Chirakkal Taluk, Malabar District. (*Hudud al-'Alam* trans. by V. Minorsky, p. 243, qt. in Nainar, *Op. cit.*, p. 31.)

29 Al-Idrisi, *Op. cit.*, p. 182; Nainar, *Op. cit.*, pp. 66, 70.

30 Utkin and Kuli lay in the Gulf of Cambay (Nainar, *Op. cit.*, p. 53).

31. *Ibn Khurdzbeh, Op. cit.*, p. 62;

الدبيل وهي أول أرض الهند.... وفي جبالها تنبت القنا الهندية. سندان...وبها تنبت القنا والخيزران. Al-Idrisi, *Op. cit.*, pp. 181-82.

32 Nainar, *Op. cit.*, p. 195.

33. وذكروا أن الكافور يكثر في سنة فيها رعود وبروق ورجف وزلازل وإن قل ذلك كان نقصا في وجوده. Al-Qazwini, *Op. cit.*, 2:68.

12. Coconut (نارجيل): Coconut is native to India. It grows all over India especially in Bullin, Kanja, Lulu, Sandan, Saymur, Subara and in the islands of *Harkand* sea. Abu Zayd narrates a startling story on making a whole ship with the coconut tree:

There are people, at Oman, who cross over the (Indian) islands that produce the coconut, carrying with them carpenters and such like tools; and having felled as much wood as they want, they let it dry, then strip off the leaves, and with the bark of the tree they spin a yarn, wherewith they sew the planks together, and so build a ship. Of the same wood they cut and round away a mast; of the leaves they weave their sails, and the bark they work into cordage. Having thus completed their vessel, they load her with coconuts, which they bring and sell at Oman. Thus is it that, from this tree alone, so many articles are convertible to use, as suffice not only to build and rig out a vessel, but to load her when she is completed, and in a trim to sail.⁴¹

13. Costus (قسط): Among the Indian agro-products is Cost us which grows in Sandan, Subara and the island of Thara.⁴² No other information about this item is found in the early Arabs' writings.

14. Crystal (بلور): None other than Ibn Khurdzbeh speaks of Crystal. It is a very rare Indian product, which is obtained from Mulay and Sandan.⁴³

15. Date Tree (النخيل): Sulaiman and Ibn al-Faqih al-Hamadani clearly affirm that there are no date trees either in China or in Hind.⁴⁴ However; Al-Idrisi differs from them to affirm that date tree grows in the island of Sandan.⁴⁵

16. Fabrics (الثوب): Reference to Indian textile occurs very rarely in the writings of early Arab geographers and travellers. Though, some are very surprised with a type of textile found in Ruhmi (Bengal). Sulaiman, Al-Mas'udi and Ibn Khurdzbeh, all talk about this stuff; yet the account of the former is adequate: 'There is a stuff made in his country (Ruhmi)

41 Abu Zayd, *Op. cit.*, pp. 85-86; See also Eusebious Renaudot, *Ancient Accounts of India and China by two Mohammedan Travellers* (London: Sam Harding, 1733), p. a: 89.

42. *Al-Idrisi, Op. cit.*, p. 182. جزيرة ثارة وهي صغيرة وفيها قليل من نارجيل وقسط.

43. *Ibn Khurdzbeh, Op. cit.*, p. 71 with *fn.a.* والذي يجيء في هذا البحر الشرقي من الصين... ومن ملي وسندان الفلفل والبلور.

44. *Ibn al-Faqih, Kitab al-Buldan*, (Leiden: E. J. Brill, 1967), p. 14. This fact is also endorsed by Istakhri, Ibn Hawqal and Maqdisi. *Elliot and Dowson, Op. cit.*, p. 38. *Nainar, Op. cit.*, pp. 66, 70.

45 *Al-Idrisi, Op. cit.*, p. 182.

which is not to be found elsewhere; so fine and delicate is this material that a dress made of it may be passed through a signet-ring. It is made of cotton and we have seen one of it.⁴⁶ Obviously the writers point to *muslin cloth* for which Bengal was well-famed in pre-British era. Later writers like Minhaj-i-Siraj (1193-1259 C.E.), Ibn Battutah and almost all European travellers offer similar information about Bengal.⁴⁷ It is widely believed that the British cut the hands of *muslin* artisans that resulted in perishing this industry.

17. Fruits (ثمر/فاكهة): Only Sulaiman and al-Idrisi talk about the fruits. As it has already been mentioned earlier that Sulaiman views that India and China did not have any date trees. They have other kinds of fruits in abundance. But in Hind pomegranate is the commonest. Al-Idrisi mentions some fruit-producing places such as Kaylkan, Lawa and Kanja.⁴⁸

We may affirm that Indian fruits draw little attention from the Arabs. This is probably due to their interest in exportable products and it is known to all that most of the fruits are putrescent, thus not suitable for export to distant lands.

18. Gold (ذهب) and Silver (فضة): Both Sulaiman and Al-Masudi affirm that gold and silver are found in *Ruhmi* (Bengal). Ibn Khurdzbeh confirms that gold is also found in *Qamarun* (Assam). They do not furnish detailed information with respect to accessibility of gold and silver in these two kingdoms.⁴⁹ These precious metals were found in plenitude in many rivers of Assam. The Tezpur grant of Vanamala affirms that the river Lauhitya (Brahmaputra) carried down gold-dust from the gold-bearing boundaries of the Kailasa Mountain. The dust of this prized metal is still found in the Brahmaputra and its tributaries.⁵⁰

46 وفي بلاده الثوب التي ليس لأحد مثلها، يدخل الثوب منها في حلقة خاتم دقة وحسنا وهو من قطن وقد رأينا بعضا منه . Abu Zaid, *Op. cit.*, p. 35; See also Eusebios Renaudot, *Op. cit.*, p.a:17; al-Mas'udi, *Op. cit.*, 132; Ibn Khurdzbeh, *Op.cit.*, 67; Elliot and Dowson, *Op.cit.*, p. 5.

47 A. Karim, *Op.cit.* p. 29.

48 نارجيل وفاكهة كثيرة . Al-Idrisi, *Op. cit.*, p. 192. These three are inland towns between Alimukam and Conjeevaram. Nainar, *Op. cit.*, p. 49.

49 وفي بلاده الذهب والفضة . Abu Zaid, *Op. cit.*, p. 36; Al-Masudi, *Op. cit.*, v. 1, p. 132; وفي بلده الذهب الكثير; Ibn Khurdzbeh, *Op. cit.*, p. 67.

50 S L Baruah, *A Comprehensive History of Assam* (New Delhi: Munshiram Monoharlal Publishers Pvt. Ltd. 1985), p. 163; B C Allen, *Assam District Gazetteers* (Calcutta: City Press 1905), v. VIII, p. 198; See also my paper..

19. Honey (عسل): Istakhri (957), Ibn Hawqal (988) and Maqdisi (940-991) affirm that a large quantity of honey is obtained in Sandan (Sindhudurg) and Saymur (Shirur).⁵¹

20. Horn of Rhino (قرن الكركدن): Watching rhino was an unprecedented experience for the Arabs. Both Sulaiman and al-Mas'udi claim that the rhino was accessible in *Ruhmi* (Bengal). Ibn Khurdzbeh asserts that it was also found in *Qamarun* (Assam). All of them were so excited with this animal that they portrayed it in full details. The horn of this animal was sold and belts were made of it on the model of gold and silver ornaments; the kings of China would wear them (i.e. belts) and elites of this country contended to wear them and exaggerated their prices to the point that they sometimes paid up to two to four thousand dinars. The interest or greed for utilizing materials made of rhino-horns had pushed this rare animal to extinction in such degree that it has become a past memory in Bengal; however, Assam still has the glory of rhino although in limited numbers.⁵²

21. Ivory (أنياب الفيلة/عاج): Generally the elephants were found all over the Indian kingdoms; mainly in *Abina* (أبينه)⁵³, *Aurnashin* (أورنشين)⁵⁴, *Kanauj* (قنوج), *Mansura* (المنصورة), *Ramini* (الرامني)⁵⁵, *Ruhmi* (رهمي) and in *Mankir* (مانكير), the kingdom of the great Indian king Balhara. However, they were found in large number in Aurnashin from where elephants had been exported to all Indian territories. The kings of India competed in the acquisition of elephants and exaggerate in their prices and they looked at them with preserving eye. Elephants were used for several purposes including war and carrying loads and goods.⁵⁶

51 Elliot and Dowson, *Op. cit.*, p. 38. Nainar, *Op. cit.*, pp. 66,70.

52 Abu Zaid, *Op. cit.*, p. 35; Eusebius Renaudot, *Op. cit.*, p. a:17; Al-Mas'udi, *Op. cit.*, pp. 132-33; ابن خردزبه... وفي بلده الذهب الكثير والكركدن *Op. cit.*, p. 67; see also this article.

53 According to Nainar (1942) *Abina* (أبينه) is Tamluk of Midnapore in West Bengal (85), while M A Rahim (1963) identified it with Burma. (1: 37).

54 The majority of history researchers agree that *Aurnashin* (أورنشين) is modern day Orissa (De Goeje, 1967: 43). However, M A Rahim alone tries to identify it with Arakan. Muhammad Abdur Rahim, *Social and Cultural History of Bengal* (Karachi: Pakistan Historical Society 1963), Vol. 1, p. 37.

55 Ibn al-Faqih al-Hamadani (1967) places *Ramini* (الرامني) after Ceylon in the Sea of *Salahit* i.e. Malacca Strait. Thus, *Ramini* may be identified with Sumatra.

56 IbnRusta, *Op. cit.*, p. 134; Al-Mas'udi, *Op. cit.*, 129.

Elephants were so friendly with the people; however, this attitude was unable to save them from the avarice of the hunters. Being hunted by voracious persons, numerous elephants lost their lives. Ivories could be purchased all over India. The hunters would sell them to brokers who would distribute this valuable and appealing material among the global dealers. Al-Idrisi refers to an experienced trader that huge amount of Indian ivories (أنياب الفيل) had been exported to Aden and other ports of Arabia and Persia.⁵⁷

22. Logwood (بقم): Many Indian lands, mainly Lulua, Kanja, Kulam would produce logwood tree or *Baqqam tree*. The plant of this tree looked like oleander. *Baqqam tree* was of two kinds; substandard quality, the other named amrun is excellent. Its fruit resembled that of carob and it posed a flavor like colocynth, thus it was not to be eaten. It is said that the root of *Baqqam tree* was utilized as an antidote for snakes' poison.⁵⁸

Here we would like to draw attention of the readers to the translation of Arabic term *baqqam* (بقم). All translators including Elliot and Nainar prefer to choose *Brazil wood* as English term for this tree. In contrast to their view we rather prefer the term logwood for the Arabic word *Baqqam*. Our writers inform that *baqqam tree* resembled oleander tree, whereas Brazil wood did not have any resemblance with oleander. On the other hand, modern dictionaries give logwood as the English term for the Arabic word *baqqam*.⁵⁹ The Arabic term, chosen by the lexicographers, for Brazil wood is *Khashab al-Barazil* (خشب البرازيل).⁶⁰ So, we think, 'logwood' is a more accurate English term for *baqqam*.

23. Mango (أنج): According to Istakhri, Ibn Hawkal and Maqdisi mangoes grew in Sindan and Saymur.⁶¹ Other writers do not provide any information about this fruit.

24. Mines: Some mineral resources -mainly sulphur and copper- have been mentioned by the Arabs. In Kullam there was a mine of yellow

57 Al-Idrisi, *Op. cit.*, p. 54.

58 اللولوا و كنجة...وينبت بأرضهما البقم كثيرا ونبات البقم شبيه بنبات الدفلى وفيها بقم يغرس Al-Idrisi, *Op. cit.*, p. 192; وكولم..وبها البقم Al-Qazwini, *Op. cit.*, 2:70; غرسا وحمله شبه الخرنوب وطعمه مثل العلقم ولا يؤكل ويقال إن عروقه شفاء من سم ساعة. Ibn al-Faqih, *Op. cit.*, p. 10.

59 Ruhi al-Ba'labakki, *Al-Mawrid* (Beirut: Dar al-'ilm li al-Malayeen, 1997), p. 244.

60 Munir al-Ba'labakki, *Al-Mawrid*, (Beirut: Dar al-'ilm li al-Malayeen, 1997), p. 125.

61 Elliot and Dowson, *Op. cit.*, p.38.

sulphur (معدن الكبريت الأصفر) and of copper (معدن النحاس). The coagulated vapour of copper makes excellent *tutiya* (zinc).⁶²

25. Myrobalan (الاهليج): It is only Yaqut who speaks about myrobalan and its kinds. A little amount of myrobalan was acquired in Kulam. But this was inferior to myrobalan obtained in Kabul, as the latter was a land-locked city and far from sea and a wide range of myrobalan was found there.

The kind of myrobalan which was dropped by the wind from ripe tree was yellow in colour, sour and cold; that which was picked up from the tree in appropriate season was called *kabuli*; it was sweet and hot; that which was left in tree during winter till its shade changed to dark was called *al-aswad*, it is bitter and acrid.⁶³

26. Pearls (اللولؤ): Only Dimishqi and al-Idrisi talk about pearls. The former notes that the city of Fufal⁶⁴ comprised a large area which includes diving places for small pearls (مغاص اللؤلؤ).⁶⁵ Another diving place for pearls was Subara; al-Idrisi informs that some inhabitants of this city would fish for pearls here.⁶⁶

27. Pepper (الفلفل): Pepper is the second most attractive Indian product (after aloewood) which allures the Arabs. Most of the early Arab geographers and travellers speak of pepper.

Pepper grew in many Indian lands, mainly in Barus, Fandarina, Jarbatan,⁶⁷ Manjarur, Malibar, Manibar,⁶⁸ Mulai, Mali, Kawlam⁶⁹ and Sandan. Mulai or Mali (Kollam in modern Kerala) was famous as *the land of pepper*, for this plant grew there in abundance. And there pepper was loaded in ships.⁷⁰

62 Qazwini, *Op. cit.*, 2:70; Elliot and Dowson, *Op. cit.*, p. 96.

63 *Ibid*, p. 200.

64 Fufal has been identified with *Bekal*.

65 Nainar, *Op. cit.*, p. 37.

66 Al-Idrisi, *Op. cit.*, p. 182; Elliot and Dowson, *Op. cit.*, p. 84.

67 وبجزيرة ملي ينبت شجر الفلفل ولا يكون إلا بها أو بفندرية أو بجرباتن ولا يوجد شيء إلا بهذه البلاد الثلاثة Al-Idrisi, *Op. cit.*, p. 182-83.

68 Malibar and Manibar are corruptions of Malabar.

69 Mulai (ملي), Mali (ملي), Kawlam (كولم) and Kwlam Mali (كولم ملي) are different corruptions of Kollam.

70 Abu Zayd, *Op. cit.*, p. 48; Nainar, *Op. cit.*, p. 47, 57.

Yaqut and Qazwini leave the following description about pepper. The pepper plant was a common one in Malibar. It was a free plant without a processor. Water was always under it. The crop dropped and shrunk as the wind blew. Then the fallen pepper was gathered from above water and the king imposed an excise on it. It would always bear a crop both summer and winter. The fruit was in bunches. When the sun was hot, a number of leaves shroud the bunch so that it might not be burned by the sun. When the sun would go off it, these leaves would also go off.⁷¹ This is evident that Yaqut and Qazwini give wrong information about the action of the leaves with the heat of the sun.

Ibn Khurdzbeh leaves much debatable description as he writes, "The navigators state that the leaves curl over the bunches to protect them from the rain and that they return to their natural position when the rain is over."⁷² Apparently this unusual description is not factual. Al-Idrisi terms it as a surprising fact.⁷³ Nainar, however, tries to give a rational explanation.⁷⁴

The *Malabari pepper* holds a strong position in international market; it is exported to the far-east and the last point of the west. And the people that gain most from pepper-trade are the Franks who carry it in the sea of Syria to the farthest west.⁷⁵

28. Perfume (النبات العطر): Al-Idrisi tells that the mountains of *Saymur* produce many aromatic plants, which are exported to the rest of the world.⁷⁶ According to Dimishqi, many brands of perfumes are found in Kulam.⁷⁷

29. Rhubarb (الرواند): Rhubarb was a gourd obtained in Kulam. It was inferior to China Rhubarb. Its leaves were the *sadaj al-Hindi* and were held in great reverence as a medicine for the eyes.⁷⁸

71 Qazwini, p. 82

72 وذكر البحرىون أن علي كل عنقود من عناقيد الفلفل ورقة تكنه من المطر فإذا انقطع المطر
ارتفعت الورقة فإذا عاد المطر عادت . Ibn Khurdzbeh, *Op. cit.*, pp. 62-63.

73 Al-Idrisi, *Op. cit.*, p. 183.

74 Nainar, *Op. cit.*, p. 202.

75 Qazwini, *Op. cit.*, 2:82. وأكثر الناس انتفاعا به الفرنج يحملونه في بحر الشام إلى أقصى المغرب

76 Al-Idrisi, *Op. cit.*, صيمور.. وبجبالها كثير من النباتات العطر المحمول إلى سائر الأفاق .
p. 182; Elliot an Dowson, *Op. cit.*, p. 85.

77 Nainar, *Op. cit.*, p. 47.

78 كولم...وبها الرواند وهو قرع ينبت هناك ورقه الساذج الهندي العزيز الوجود لأجل أدوية
العين . Qazwini, *Op. cit.*, p. 2:70.

- 30. Rice (أرز):** Rice was the most common Indian paddy which grew all over the country, particularly in Babattan, Bullin, Jabartan, Kanja, Kaylkan, Kuli, Samandar, Sinjili, Sandan, Saymur and other areas. Rice, not wheat, was their main food.⁷⁹
- 31. Sandal Wood (الصنديل):** Sandal wood was not a common Indian plant. It grew only in the plains and mountains of Mandari and Najaba.⁸⁰
- 32. Sandarac (سندروس):** A little amount of Sandarac, a rare product of India, was found in Kulam. This was of inferior quality, while the better quality was found in China.⁸¹
- 33. Sandals (النعال):** Al-Mas'udi mentions a brand of sandal known as *Kanbayan* made in a city of the same name and in the neighbouring towns like Sandan and Subara.⁸²
- 34. Magnet stone (مغناطيس):** Magnetized stone was found in Kulam. When it was heated by scraping, it magnetized things.⁸³
- 35. Teak (ساج):** India was famous for its high quality teak tree, which grew in many areas particularly in Kulam and Sandan.⁸⁴ However, it was produced in such quantity in Kamkam⁸⁵ that this land was known as *the land of teak* (بلاد الساج). And the species grown in Kulam was huge and tall, exceeding even a hundred cubits.⁸⁶
- 36. Vases (غضائر):** Vases were manufactured in Kulam and sold in Arab countries in the name of Chinese brand, but they were not Chinese, for the Chinese clay was harder than Kulam clay and more fire-resisting. And the Kulam vases were blackish, while those of China were white and of other colours.⁸⁷

79 Ibn Khurdzbeh, *Op. cit.*, p. 63, Al-Idrisi, *Op. cit.*, pp. 181, 189, 191-95, 197. Al-Hamadani, *Op. cit.*, p. 14

80 Ibn Rusta, *Op. cit.*, p. 135. ولهم الصنديل الأحمر في بلادهم وغيابهم.

81 Nainar, *Op. cit.*, p. 205.

82 Nainar, *Op. cit.*, p. 205-06.

83 Nainar, *Op. cit.*, p. 206.

84 بلهرا إنه ملك ملوك الهند وهو؛ Ibn Khurdzbeh, *Op. cit.*, p. 67; وبها ساج وقتنا
Ibn Rusta, *Op. cit.*, p. 134 في بلاده يقال له الكمكم.. وبلاده بلاد الساج ومنها يجلب

85 Kamkam has been identified with *Konkan*. The ancient and medieval *Konkan* has been distributed in modern map among some coastal districts of western Indian states of Maharashtra, Goa and Karnataka, namely Mumbai, Palghar, Raigad, Ratnagiri, Sindhudurg, North Goa and South Goa. Nainar, *Op. cit.*, 41; <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Konkan>.

86 Qazwini, *Op. cit.*, 2:70. وبها منابت الساج المفرط الطول ربما جاوز مائة ذراع وأكثر

87 كولم.. وتعمل بها غضائر تباع في بلادنا على أنه صيني وليس كذلك لأن طين الصين أبيض وغيره من طين كولم وأصبر على النار وغضائر كولم لونها أدكن وغضائر الصين أبيض وغيره من الألوان. Al-Qazwini, *Op. cit.*, p. 2:70; Nainar, *Op. cit.*, p. 206.

37. Wheat (حنطة): Wheat grew in Kaylkan, Lawa and Kanja; but Indians did not normally eat wheat; their main food was rice.⁸⁸

Conclusion

In this paper I have described exportable India commodities as narrated by the early Arab geographers and travellers. It has been observed that ancient India and the Bengal region had many products which commanded immense demand in the international markets. It has also been reflected here that our writers' interest was confined to the exportable goods of India; thus their writings became guidebooks for the traders. Those accounts are still considered important registers of information about ancient and early mediaeval India.

⁸⁸ Ibn Khurdazbeh, *Op. cit.*, p. 63; Al-Hamadani, *Op. cit.*, p. 14.